

EXPORT COMPETITIVENESS OF MAJOR AGRICULTURAL COMMODITIES FROM INDIA DURING PRE AND POST REFORM PERIOD

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Abstract:

Agriculture is one of the most sensitive economic sectors all over the world. Nevertheless, agricultural exports have several economic benefits. It can help to stimulate a wide array of industries linked to agriculture, including transportation, processing, and farm input suppliers. In 1991, the Government of India introduced series of economic reforms to liberalize and globalize Indian economy. Since the initiation of economic reforms, India's outward orientation has started increasing. The agricultural exports growth rate is remarkable with the growth of 17.66 per cent, at 3.33 lakh crore in 2020-21. The main objective of the present study is to analyze the export competitiveness of major agricultural commodities from India during pre and post reform period. Data used for this study were collected from various secondary sources like UNCOMTRADE, FAOSTAT, WTO, etc. The study period between 1980-81 and 2019-20 is divided into two sub periods i.e., pre reform (1980-81 to 1990-91) and post reform (1991-92 to 2019-20) period. To analyze the data we employed Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA). The results revealed that among the selected agricultural commodities spices have higher RCA values in both the periods hence; India has more comparative advantage in spice exports. Therefore, the policy and reforms of the GOI had impacted majorly in post reform period and had a still large gap and scope that can be filled up by new policies and initiatives for the export of the other agricultural commodities.

Key words: Agricultural exports, Pre and Post Reform period, Revealed Comparative Advantage

Introduction

Agriculture is one of the most sensitive economic sector. Nevertheless agricultural exports have several economic benefits. It can help to stimulate a wide array of industries linked to agriculture, transportation, processing, and farm input suppliers. India took a series of successful agricultural revolutions, including the "white" revolution in milk in the late 1970s and the "yellow" revolution in oilseeds in the 1980s, whereas the green revolution focused on wheat and rice which made it possible to achieve food security (Pathak *et al.*, 2022).

India is a global powerhouse of agriculture as it is the largest producer and exporter of spices, pulses, milk, cashew, tea, tobacco, sugarcane, cotton, etc (Shinoj and Mathur, 2008; Saxena and Nath, 2012; Ramesh *et al.*, 2017). India accounts for more than 8 percent of spices, coffee and tea, vegetable (1.7-1.8 %), marine products (5.9 %), and many more products having export demands earning in the international market.

Foreign trade plays a significant role in the growth and development of an economic system towards enhancement of level of production, generation of income, and creation of employment, the inflow of foreign exchange at the domestic level, and empowerment of bilateral and multilateral economic relations at the global level. Introduction of Foreign Trade Policy has facilitated augmenting exports from India and in maintaining a favorable balance of payment.

Before the trade liberalization 1991, the western economies adhered to laissez-faire economic principles and used to place a higher value on private investment. After World War II the western countries adopted Marxist policies that made them dominant over the underdeveloped countries. The agriculture sector was given less importance than the manufacturing sector. Throughout the 1980s India adopted an inward-looking approach policy which was characterized by higher tariff rates, licensing, and quantitative limitations and the domestic markets were protected from fluctuation in the market due to "price protection policies".

The Indian government took various policy measures to build the economy and to improve the balance of payments. Thus, GOI introduced the New Economic Policy (NEP-1991) with respect to trade, monetary & financial policies and institutional and price policy reforms. The salient features of NEP-1991 were Economic liberalization, Extending privatization Globalization of economy and Market friendly economy

Several policy measures were initiated to boost agriculture export namely AEP (Agriculture export policy), EPF (Export promotion Forums) for specific products, and Agri-cells in 13 different countries which is helping in real-time trade data. Further, to combat freight

disadvantages relaxed using schemes like TIES (Trade Infrastructure for Export Scheme), MAI (Market Access Initiatives), and TMA (Transport and Marketing Assistance) for agricultural export.

Material And Methods

The study conducted was based on secondary data collected from various published sources like UNCOMTRADE, FAOSTAT, WTO, etc. The data was grouped as Pre reform (1980- 81 to 1990-91) and Post reform (1991-92 to 2019-20) period. Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) was calculated to analyze the export competitiveness of major agricultural commodities from India during pre and post reform period. For the present study, the commodities like tea, coffee, rice, tobacco, spices and cashew were considered which are majorly exported from India.

Balassa Index-Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA)

The concept of revealed comparative advantage pertains to the relative trade performance of individual countries in particular commodities. On the assumption that the commodity pattern of trade reflects the inter-country differences in relative costs as well as in non-price factors, this is assumed to "reveal" the comparative advantage of the trading countries. The factors that contribute to movements in RCA are economic: structural change, improved world demand and trade specialization.

Balassa (1965) first introduced the concept of Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA). Balassa's measure of relative export performance by country and commodity, defined as a country's share of world exports of a commodity divided by its share of total world exports. The index for country i commodity j is calculated as follows:

$$RCA_{ij} = (X_{ij}/X_{wj})/(X_i/X_w)$$

Where

X_{ij} = ith country's export of commodity j

X_{wj} = world exports of commodity j

X_i = total exports of country i

X_w = total world exports

RCA was calculated for six major agricultural commodities for a period from 1980-81 to 1990-91 and 1991-92 to 2019-20 and values are presented in tables. The RCA was measured using pre and post trade data. The index of revealed comparative advantage (RCA_{ij}) has a relatively simple interpretation. If it takes a value greater than unity, the country has a revealed comparative advantage in that product whereas the country has revealed comparative disadvantage in that product if RCA value is less than unity.

The advantage of using the comparative advantage index is that it considers the intrinsic advantage of a particular export commodity and is consistent with changes in an economy's relative factor endowment and productivity. The disadvantage, however, is that it cannot distinguish improvements in factor endowments and pursuit of appropriate trade policies by a country.

Results And Discussion

Export competitiveness for major agricultural commodities

Comparative Advantage of major agricultural commodities exported from India during pre reform period

The results for the comparative advantage of major agricultural commodities exported from India during pre reform period are presented in the Table 4.1. This shows that among the selected agricultural commodities spices had the highest RCA values about 6.0399 and 5.6234 and 5.2538 crores during 1988-89, 1989-90 and 1990-91 respectively, since the Indian agro-climatic conditions are the most suitable for spices production and meanwhile since memorable Indian spices holds global market share and creates a monopoly in the global market. Followed by tobacco and tea however, coffee and cashew had least RCA values in the pre reform period.

Comparative Advantage of major agricultural commodities exported from India during post reform period

The results for the comparative advantage of major agricultural commodities exported from India during post reform period are presented in the Table 4.2. This shows that tea RCA value was highest (2.2198) during 2012-13 and lowest (0.8532) during 2001-02. In the case of coffee, the highest RCA value was observed (4.6322) during 2009-10 and the lowest (1.0389) during 1991-92. The highest RCA value was observed in 2011-12 for Rice (3.2172) however lowest (0.8358) was in 2005-06. In the case of tobacco, the highest RCA value was observed (3.5560) during 2015-16, however lowest was observed (0.9401) during 2017-18. With regard to cashew highest RCA value was 4.5967 during 2009-10 and the lowest (0.2495) during 2019-20. In the case of spices, the highest RCA value was during 2019-20 (9.3744) and the lowest (4.0532) during 1992-93.

During the post reform period, spices had the highest RCA value since after the reforms there is no stiff competition from other countries as compared to other commodities. As Indian spices are known for their flavor and aroma, and people are also conscious of their health benefits. Thus spices had the highest comparative advantage. The results are in line with Mohit *et al.* (2016).

Conclusion

Agriculture being a very crucial sector shows ductile behavior in the Indian economy. Based on the above analysis, it can be concluded that among the selected agricultural commodities spices have higher RCA values in both the periods therefore; India has more comparative advantage in spice exports. With the establishment of WTO and India being a signatory to AOA along with other trade commitments, destinations of trade have switched from developed to developing countries, thus proving advantageous for Exports.

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Table 4.1: Comparative Advantage of major agricultural commodities exported from India during Pre reform period (1980-81 to 1990-91)

Value: ₹ in Crores

Year/Commodity	Tea	Coffee	Rice	Tobacco	Spices	Cashew
1980-81	1.0556	0.8860	1.5663	1.0444	0.8029	0.5105
1981-82	0.9016	0.7899	0.9791	1.0258	0.9155	0.4517
1982-83	1.0121	0.9327	0.7839	1.0926	1.0357	0.4336
1983-84	1.0001	0.9998	0.9997	1.1444	1.0003	0.1315
1984-85	0.9999	0.9999	1.0001	1.1844	1.0001	0.5887
1985-86	0.6462	0.9693	0.9984	1.2414	1.0007	0.5788
1986-87	1.0005	1.0011	0.9984	1.2722	1.0003	0.8269
1987-88	1.0115	1.0006	1.0012	1.2533	1.0778	0.6123
1988-89	1.0104	1.0533	0.9987	1.2549	6.0399	0.9668
1989-90	1.0125	1.0170	1.0004	1.1969	5.6234	1.1095
1990-91	1.0083	1.0543	1.0008	1.3595	5.2538	1.1202

Table 4.2: Comparative Advantage of major agricultural commodities exported from India during Post reform period (1991-92 to 2019-20)

Value: ₹ in Crores

Year/ Commodity	Tea	Coffee	Rice	Tobacco	Spices	Cashew
1991-92	1.0135	1.0389	1.0006	1.2002	4.3837	1.1944
1992-93	1.0286	1.2150	1.0004	1.3331	4.0532	1.1206
1993-94	1.0212	1.2303	1.0003	1.2519	4.8307	1.2129
1994-95	1.0117	1.1587	1.0002	1.3849	5.4249	1.1223
1995-96	1.0110	1.2235	1.0000	1.1804	5.4170	1.1570
1996-97	1.0275	1.2425	0.9999	1.1461	6.3876	1.0993
1997-98	1.0122	1.2962	2.9937	1.1589	5.8102	1.0678
1998-99	1.0489	1.2361	1.0000	1.3315	5.8134	1.0617
1999-00	1.0204	1.2524	0.9995	1.2419	5.8645	1.2060
2000-01	2.1495	1.3777	0.9721	1.3351	4.6784	0.8868
2001-02	0.8532	1.2963	1.0913	1.3620	4.3075	2.9631
2002-03	1.0069	1.3622	0.9797	1.2917	4.6462	2.9897
2003-04	1.0570	1.4059	0.9175	1.3723	4.4369	0.7732
2004-05	0.9750	1.3916	2.1613	1.2907	4.8352	1.7922
2005-06	0.9873	2.4760	0.8358	1.2686	4.9314	0.7670
2006-07	1.0055	1.3192	1.0242	1.2895	6.5094	0.7397
2007-08	1.0441	1.4165	3.1113	1.3066	7.7696	0.5811
2008-09	1.0377	1.2445	0.8493	1.3889	7.8640	0.5848
2009-10	1.1103	4.6322	1.9811	1.2287	7.2352	4.5967
2010-11	0.9357	3.5292	0.9783	1.0830	5.3691	0.4823
2011-12	0.9693	1.3693	3.2172	3.4430	6.5450	0.6026
2012-13	2.2198	1.3629	1.9789	1.2738	8.5152	0.5134
2013-14	1.0551	2.4915	1.0184	1.2858	8.3592	1.6853
2014-15	1.0643	3.5416	1.0173	1.4275	7.6067	0.5330
2015-16	1.0722	1.4599	1.9223	3.5560	6.8838	0.3965
2016-17	1.0436	1.4453	1.0180	1.3473	6.6528	0.3338
2017-18	1.0570	1.4718	1.0697	0.9401	7.7223	1.3208
2018-19	1.0631	4.5546	1.0268	0.9460	7.7591	0.2553
2019-2020	1.0470	3.5169	0.9727	0.9875	9.3744	0.2495